

Simulated millennial-scale climate variability driven by a convection-advection oscillator

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Abstract

The last glacial period, between around 115 and 12 thousand years before present, exhibited strong millennial-scale climate variability. This includes abrupt transitions between cold and warm climates, known as Dansgaard-Oeschger (D-O) cycles. D-O cycles have been linked to switches in dynamical regimes of the Atlantic Overturning Meridional Circulation (AMOC), but the exact mechanisms behind abrupt climate changes and AMOC regime shifts remain poorly understood.

This paper introduces the convection-advection oscillator mechanism to explain the millennial-scale oscillations observed in a set of HadCM3 general circulation model simulations forced with snapshots of deglacial meltwater history. The oscillator can be separated into two components acting on different time scales. The fast convection component responds to changes in vertical stratification in the North Atlantic by activating or deactivating deep water formation sites. The slow advection component regulates the accumulation and depletion of salinity in the North Atlantic.

This oscillator mechanism is triggered under specific background conditions and freshwater release patterns. The freshwater perturbation causes an instability that triggers a global salt reorganisation, modifying the North Atlantic stratification. For a given forcing pattern, the system oscillates if the salt transport can lead to an alternating reactivation and deactivation of the AMOC. Otherwise, the climate settles in a warm or cold steady state. This mechanism expands existing theories of millennial-scale variability and provides a general framework for understanding abrupt climate change in general circulation models.

Keywords: Millennial-scale variability, AMOC, General circulation model, Salt oscillator, North Atlantic stratification, convection-advection oscillator

1 Introduction

Millennial-scale variability during the last glacial period

1 The Greenland ice core records of the last glacial period, stretching between about 115
2 and about 12 ka BP (thousand years before present), are dominated by millennial-scale
3 variability (Wolff et al, 2010). Dansgaard-Oeschger (D-O) cycles (Dansgaard et al,
4 1993; Bond et al, 1993), recurring transitions between cold *stadial* and warm *intersta-*
5 *dial* North Atlantic climates (Thomas et al, 2009; Lohmann and Ditlevsen, 2019), are
6 the most prominent example of such variability. During these transitions, Greenland
7 underwent temperature changes of up to 16 °C (Huber et al, 2006; Kindler et al, 2014;
8 Buizert et al, 2014) within a few decades (Rasmussen et al, 2014). North Atlantic
9 abrupt climate changes have been widely associated with changes in the Atlantic
10 Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC, Rahmstorf, 2002; Clark et al, 2002). This
11 is primarily because the AMOC is believed to have shifted between different modes
12 during the last glacial period (Broecker et al, 1985; Gottschalk et al, 2015; Henry et al,
13 2016; Lynch-Stieglitz, 2017; Weijer et al, 2019), disrupting the flux of heat and salt
14 into the North Atlantic. Three dynamical regimes of the AMOC have been hypothe-
15 sised by Rahmstorf (2002): a *warm* mode where a vigorous AMOC reaches up to 70°N,

16 a *cold* mode where a shallower AMOC does not extend past the Greenland-Iceland-
17 Scotland (GIS) ridge, and an *off* mode where the AMOC is collapsed (Böhm et al,
18 2015). Simulations of the climate of the next centuries (Weijer et al, 2020; Romanou
19 et al, 2023) and observed fingerprints of potential decline in AMOC strength (Thor-
20 nalley et al, 2018; Caesar et al, 2018; Boers, 2021; Michel et al, 2022; Ditlevsen and
21 Ditlevsen, 2023) have raised concerns that the AMOC might undergo an abrupt weak-
22 ening or collapse again with potentially dramatic consequences on the North Atlantic
23 climate (van Westen et al, 2024).

24 However, the climate projections are highly model-dependent (Weijer et al, 2020;
25 Bellomo et al, 2021) and direct observations are still too short to draw any statistically
26 significant conclusion on potential shifts in the AMOC regime (Lobelle et al, 2020;
27 Jackson et al, 2022). Reducing the uncertainty in future AMOC stability requires a
28 deeper understanding of the dynamic processes driving the overturning circulation,
29 which can be examined through climate modelling of the last glacial period. In partic-
30 ular, the Last Glacial Maximum (LGM) – about 21 ka BP – and marine isotope stage
31 3 – about 60 ka BP to 30 ka BP – have proven insightful for studying AMOC stability
32 (Weijer et al, 2019). Freshwater hosing experiments have historically been an effective
33 way to trigger abrupt climate changes in most climate models (Manabe and Stouffer,
34 1995; Kageyama et al, 2010; Hawkins et al, 2011; Kageyama et al, 2013; van Westen
35 and Dijkstra, 2023). When it comes to simulating spontaneous oscillations, however,
36 General Circulation Models (GCMs) were for a long time regarded as too biased
37 towards producing more stable climates (Valdes, 2011; Mecking et al, 2017; Liu et al,
38 2017). This bias was addressed by making use of modern supercomputers to explore
39 a comprehensive range of model inputs (including uncertain model parameters and
40 climate forcings) and running models for multiple millennia. As a result, more GCMs
41 have been found to exhibit millennial-scale variability in the past decade (e.g., Peltier

42 and Vettoretti, 2014; Brown and Galbraith, 2016; Klockmann et al, 2018; Zhang et al,
43 2021; Armstrong et al, 2022; Kuniyoshi et al, 2022; Malmierca-Vallet et al, 2023).

44 Barker and Knorr (2021) coined the term ‘window of opportunity’ to define a
45 model parameter regime where millennial-scale variability can occur. Not all models
46 share the same windows of opportunity, i.e. the location and extent of the window of
47 opportunity in the parameter space varies across models. Most models agree, however,
48 on the most relevant parameters that determine its definition; namely the atmo-
49 spheric greenhouse gases, orbital parameters, ice sheet topography and freshwater
50 release. Atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (Brown and Galbraith, 2016; Zhang et al,
51 2017; Klockmann et al, 2018; Vettoretti et al, 2022; Malmierca-Vallet et al, 2024) and
52 insolation (Zhang et al, 2021; Kuniyoshi et al, 2022) are essential to the creation of
53 conditions facilitating abrupt climate change through their influence on the Atlantic
54 energy balance, atmospheric and oceanic circulations and stratification. The ice sheet
55 configuration is equally important, as the extensive ice sheets covering North America
56 and northern Europe during the last glacial maximum (Hughes et al, 2016; Batchelor
57 et al, 2019) act to prevent the occurrence of AMOC mode shifts (Zhang et al, 2014;
58 Brown and Galbraith, 2016; Klockmann et al, 2018). Glacial ice sheets tend to drive a
59 less variable, more southern and potentially faster eddy-driven jet (Merz et al, 2015;
60 Li and Born, 2019). This results in stronger surface winds and wind stress curl that
61 intensify the salt and heat transport to the deep water formation sites (Czaja, 2009;
62 Montoya et al, 2011; Sherriff-Tadano et al, 2018, 2021). The topography and albedo
63 of the ice sheets also modify the inter-hemispheric heat fluxes (Roberts and Valdes,
64 2017). In addition, glacial ice sheets can produce larger freshwater fluxes than the
65 pre-industrial ice sheets, as observed in sea level records of the last glacial period (Fair-
66 banks, 1989; Lambeck et al, 2014). This is another critical input because freshwater
67 can enhance ocean stratification by decreasing the surface layer density, reducing deep

68 convection and thereby weakening the AMOC. Freshwater forcing is particularly effi-
69 cient at slowing down the AMOC when targeted at regions of deep water formation,
70 such as within the Nordic Seas (Smith and Gregory, 2009; Roche et al, 2010), but the
71 exact rate and location of freshwater release during the last glacial period discharge
72 events remains challenging to constrain (Birchfield et al, 1994; Bethke et al, 2012).

Mechanisms of millennial-scale variability

73 With his pioneering box model, Stommel (1961) demonstrated that heat and salt
74 fluxes between two interconnected basins could lead to two distinct stable regimes of
75 ocean circulation. This hypothesis was influential in the establishment of theories for
76 AMOC regime shifts in the context of millennial-scale variability. The most famous
77 of such was the salt oscillator mechanism introduced by Broecker et al (1990). In
78 this theory, when the AMOC is weak, salt is accumulated in the Atlantic by evapo-
79 ration and increases the surface density, leading to the reactivation of North Atlantic
80 vertical convection and the overturning circulation. When the AMOC is strong, the
81 overturning circulation exports salt out of the Atlantic basin and the surface den-
82 sity decreases, leading to the deactivation of North Atlantic deep water formation
83 sites and a weakening of the overturning circulation. The validity of this mechanism
84 depends on the sign of the net salt export out of the Atlantic Ocean (Huisman et al,
85 2010; Drijfhout et al, 2011), and an initial perturbation is required to start the oscil-
86 lator. Millennial-scale variability can also arise from local instabilities. Spontaneous
87 oscillations in a simple mixed-layer model were demonstrated by Welander (1982),
88 and Cessi (1996) argued that a freshwater input could trigger this oscillator. Winton
89 and Sarachik (1993) also explored the role of vertical instability of the water column
90 to introduce the concept of deep-decoupling oscillations. Deep-decoupling oscillations
91 rely on the different response times between the surface and the deep North Atlantic
92 waters, and the building and collapse of the halocline in the North Atlantic deactivates

93 or reactivates deep convection. [Colin de Verdière \(2007\)](#) proposed a model where the
94 salt-oscillator theory described by [Broecker et al \(1990\)](#) and the vertical mixed-layer
95 oscillations of [Welander \(1982\)](#) work in concert to produce millennial-scale oscillations.
96 Finally, stochastic resonance was suggested as another possible mechanism to trigger
97 abrupt regime shifts ([Alley et al, 2001](#); [Ganopolski and Rahmstorf, 2002](#); [Cimatoribus](#)
98 [et al, 2013](#)). This theory relies on stochastic noise to amplify internal ocean variability
99 and kick-start oscillations ([Schulz et al, 2002](#); [Timmermann et al, 2003](#)).

100 An effective framework for comparing complex climate model simulations with
101 theoretical models is to conceptualise millennial-scale variability mechanisms as a
102 combination of slow and fast components ([Roberts and Saha, 2017](#); [Vettoretti et al,](#)
103 [2022](#)). Slow components modify the atmospheric and oceanic conditions in the North
104 Atlantic, while fast components consist of a combination of thresholds and positive
105 feedbacks that can rapidly alter deep water formation activity. Although the scope
106 and definition of the salt oscillator has varied since its introduction ([Broecker et al,](#)
107 [1990](#)), it remains a central concept to describe the slow components (e.g. [Vettoretti](#)
108 [and Peltier, 2018](#); [Klockmann et al, 2020](#); [Armstrong et al, 2022](#)). [Vettoretti and](#)
109 [Peltier \(2018\)](#) showed that southwards transport of Arctic sea ice was responsible for
110 the freshening of the North Atlantic prior to a cooling event, and the northwards gyre
111 transportation of salt into the North Atlantic was responsible for the salinification of
112 the North Atlantic prior to a warming event. In [Klockmann et al \(2020\)](#)'s simulations,
113 phases of accumulation and depletion of the subtropical Atlantic salinity affect the
114 density gradient across the subpolar gyre. Similar to [Broecker et al \(1990\)](#), [Armstrong](#)
115 [et al \(2022\)](#)'s analysis points towards changes in Atlantic precipitation and evaporation
116 patterns due to shifts of the ITCZ. Additionally, they discuss the influence of sea ice
117 transport on the meridional salinity gradients in the North Atlantic. In [Kuniyoshi et al](#)
118 [\(2022\)](#)'s study, sea ice transport is also the main driver of the mechanisms, although
119 thermal changes of the North Atlantic water column are more impactful than changes

120 in surface salinity gradient. Thermal control of millennial-scale oscillations was equally
121 considered in previous works (e.g., [Oka et al, 2012](#); [Dokken et al, 2013](#); [Brown and](#)
122 [Galbraith, 2016](#)). Additionally, sources of salt and heat outside of the North Atlantic,
123 such as the Southern Ocean ([Knorr and Lohmann, 2003](#); [Banderas et al, 2015](#); [Buiz-](#)
124 [ert and Schmittner, 2015](#); [Thompson et al, 2019](#); [Oka et al, 2021](#)) or the Indian Ocean
125 ([Nuber et al, 2023](#)), were also identified as potential drivers of slow changes of the
126 North Atlantic water masses. This is the case, for instance, in the mechanism by [Vet-](#)
127 [toretti et al \(2022\)](#) where the density of the AABW modifies the Atlantic vertical
128 stratification. Finally, [Weijer and Dijkstra \(2003\)](#) argues that a salinity anomaly that
129 propagates along the different ocean basins could set the pacing of the oscillations.

130 The fast dynamics involve positive feedback that can accelerate the reactivation
131 and deactivation of the deep water formation sites when one or several North Atlantic
132 climate thresholds. The salt-advection feedback ([Drijfhout et al, 2015](#); [Weijer et al,](#)
133 [2019](#)) is a central concept here: a stronger AMOC advects more salt to the deep
134 water formation sites, enhancing deep convection which further amplifies the AMOC.
135 Conversely, a decrease in AMOC strength further weakens the AMOC by advecting less
136 salt northwards, reducing surface density at the deep convection sites. This is at stake,
137 for instance, in [Kuniyoshi et al \(2022\)](#) and [Vettoretti and Peltier \(2018\)](#)'s mechanism,
138 where the positive feedback accelerates the initial changes in North Atlantic deep water
139 formation when the vertical stratification in the region passes a certain threshold. In
140 other instances, the feedback can amplify the impact of exceptional events, such as the
141 opening of polynyas to release abruptly the heat accumulated under the surface of the
142 ice (a phenomenon referred to as subsurface warming) in [Vettoretti and Peltier \(2016\)](#).
143 Both the threshold and exceptional events approaches were considered in [Klockmann](#)
144 [et al \(2020\)](#), building on the theory introduced by [Li and Born \(2019\)](#), to describe
145 a positive feedback between the winds and the subpolar gyre leading to shifts in the
146 North Atlantic convection. This feedback can be activated either by a change in the

147 cross-gyre density gradient or by stochastic wind forcing. In [Armstrong et al \(2022\)](#),
148 the meridional density gradient in the North Atlantic acts as the threshold, and both
149 the wind-driven and the salt advection feedbacks accelerate the changes in North
150 Atlantic convection. [Kuniyoshi et al \(2022\)](#) describes a sea-ice positive feedback that
151 cools down the North Atlantic during an interstadial to stadial transition. Finally,
152 external forcing such as the freshwater input used in [Brown and Galbraith \(2016\)](#) and
153 the change of vertical diffusivity in [Peltier and Vettoretti \(2014\)](#) can act as the initial
154 trigger of the fast components.

Objectives of the paper

155 The Hadley Centre Climate Model 3, also known as HadCM3 ([Valdes et al, 2017](#)), is
156 one of the models that has managed to simulate abrupt climate changes under realistic
157 glacial conditions. Signs of AMOC transitions were previously reported in response
158 to freshwater forcing ([Matero et al, 2017](#); [Ivanovic et al, 2018](#)), but only recently
159 did two independent studies manage to observe oscillations of the North Atlantic
160 climate: [Romé et al \(2022\)](#) triggered oscillations using deglacial meltwater patterns
161 in a last glacial maximum background state and [Armstrong et al \(2022\)](#) described
162 oscillations that occur for a specific snapshot of marine isotope stage 3 conditions
163 (30 ka BP boundary conditions). In this work, we aim to analyse the processes at
164 stake in the LGM simulations presented in [Romé et al \(2022\)](#) and explore how they
165 connect to other mechanisms derived from HadCM3 and other model simulations. We
166 do not try to directly identify the mechanisms behind D-O cycles, as the experimental
167 design prevents a direct comparison. After presenting the experimental design of the
168 simulations (Section 2) and summarising the results and terminology introduced by
169 [Romé et al \(2022\)](#) (Section 3), we separately examine the changes in stratification at
170 the North Atlantic convection sites (Section 4.1) as well as the global salt exchanges

171 (Section 4.2). Section 5 brings these insights together to introduce the convection-
172 advection oscillator mechanism. Section 6 analyses how our mechanism applies to
173 non-oscillating simulations and could help characterise AMOC stability in general
174 circulation models. Finally, Section 7 explores the limitations of this theory and how
175 it connects to previous mechanisms for millennial-scale variability.

2 Methods

2.1 The HadCM3 general circulation model

176 All the simulations in this study used the BRIDGE (Bristol Research Initiative
177 for the Dynamic Global Environment group) version of the HadCM3 (HadCM3B)
178 atmosphere-ocean general circulation model developed by Valdes et al (2017). The
179 atmosphere model, described by Pope et al (2000), consists of a $2.5^\circ \times 3.75^\circ$ grid on 19
180 elevation levels. The ocean model, described by Gordon et al (2000), is a $1.25^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$
181 grid on 20 depth layers. In order to verify the equation of state (Bryan and Cox, 1972;
182 Fofonoff and Millard Jr, 1983; Fofonoff, 1985), the ocean model uses a rigid surface lid
183 (Gordon et al, 2000), meaning that the ocean volume stays constant throughout the
184 simulations. In addition to the ocean and atmosphere components, the model includes
185 the MOSES 2.1 land model (Cox et al, 1999) and the TRIFFID dynamic vegetation
186 model (Cox, 2001). The land-sea mask is matched to the chosen palaeo ice sheet recon-
187 struction. The Gibraltar Strait is closed during the LGM – as it is for the present,
188 due to the spatial resolution of the model – and Mediterranean-Atlantic salt and heat
189 exchanges are parametrised by a diffusive pipe (Ivanovic et al, 2013, 2014). HadCM3B
190 was optimised for multi-millennial palaeoclimate runs (Valdes et al, 2017) and has
191 been used previously for glacial simulations with an imposed meltwater forcing (e.g.,
192 Ivanovic et al, 2018; Romé et al, 2022).

2.2 Global mean salinity conservation

193 HadCM3 uses a rigid-lid ocean model to compute water fluxes. The rigid-lid model
194 implies that the volume of the ocean remains constant throughout the simulations,
195 and water fluxes, whether they are freshwater discharge, precipitation or evaporation,
196 are implemented in the model as a change of the surface layer salinity rather than
197 a physical input of water. This also means that the land-sea mask is not updated in
198 response to the freshwater fluxes in such experiments.

199 This method does not guarantee the closing of the hydrological budgets caus-
200 ing shifts in the global mean salinity. Global mean salinity drifts of the order of
201 $0.25 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ kyr}^{-1}$ can spontaneously occur in HadCM3 even without freshwater input
202 (Dentith et al, 2019). In other cases, global salinity increase can also be observed
203 if the model configuration is biased towards higher evaporation than precipitation,
204 leading to salt accumulation in inland seas and the tropical oceans. On top of these
205 background shifts in global salinity, an input of meltwater of around 0.1 Sv, the order
206 of magnitude of the discharge used in this study, can drive a significant decrease in
207 salinity comparable to that observed during the last deglaciation over 10.000 years of
208 simulations.

209 The aim of this set of simulations is not to simulate a deglaciation and the continued
210 freshening of the global ocean during the long integration should be avoided. To tackle
211 this issue, we use a global salinity conservation algorithm – this corresponds to the
212 *VFLUX* method described by Dentith et al (2019). The *VFLUX* algorithm sets a
213 global mean salinity target (shortened salinity target in the following) for the entire
214 run. At the end of each time step, the model corrects the salinity uniformly throughout
215 each depth so that the corrected global mean salinity matches the value of the salinity
216 target. The global mean salinity target is calculated from the 1950 CE (Common Era)
217 global mean salinity, adjusted to account for the differences in the ice sheets volume
218 between the present and a given point in time. Note that the change in salinity target

Table 1 Experiments summary. All experiments were designed with LGM boundary conditions, using the LGM GLAC-1D ice sheet extent and associated geographies. The *meltwater* entries indicate the meltwater snapshot used (see Section 2.3) and the total meltwater flux in brackets. The meltwater flux only corresponds to the freshwater from the ice sheet melting and does not include the other freshwater fluxes (e.g., precipitation, sea ice, etc.). The *Salinity Target* ($g.kg^{-1}$) entries are the global salinity target used for the salinity correction described in Section 2.2. *Tendencies* indicates if the salinity tendencies diagnostic described in S6 were included.

Simulation name	Meltwater snapshot <i>Meltwater flux (Sv)</i>	Integration length (years)	Salinity Target ($g.kg^{-1}$)	Tendencies (included)
<i>CTRL_LGM</i>	None	4,000	35.8334	No
<i>20.7k</i>	20.7 ka BP (<i>0.084</i>)	10,000	35.8225	No
<i>21k</i>	21.0 ka BP (<i>0.054</i>)	4,000	35.8334	No
<i>18.2k</i>	18.2 ka BP (<i>0.109</i>)	10,000	35.7348	No
<i>20.7k.tdc</i>	20.7 ka BP (<i>0.084</i>)	4,000	35.8225	Yes
<i>20.7k.no.gst</i>	20.7 ka BP (<i>0.084</i>)	3,000	None	No

219 only covers ice volume changes and does not take into account additional freshwater
 220 input. The new salinity target is implemented at the start of each simulation, and a
 221 transient regime where the model adjusts to the new conditions can be observed in
 222 the initial millennium (Romé et al, 2022).

2.3 Experimental design

223 The simulations in this paper, presented in Table 1, are branched from the *CTRL_LGM*
 224 (or *control*) simulation at year 0. The *control* simulation is a last glacial maximum
 225 run following the 21 ka BP PMIP4 protocol for the boundary conditions (greenhouse
 226 gas concentrations, orbital parameters and solar constant, Kageyama et al, 2017). We
 227 used the GLAC-1D (Tarasov and Peltier, 2002; Tarasov et al, 2012; Briggs et al, 2014;
 228 Ivanovic et al, 2016) ice sheet reconstruction and the corresponding land-sea mask,
 229 orography and bathymetry. *CTRL_LGM* extends a previous HadCM3 last glacial max-
 230 imum simulation (Davies-Barnard et al, 2017), and starts after an initial 3,500 years
 231 spin-up with the updated boundary conditions. *CTRL_LGM*'s start year will be the
 232 year 0 in our time series.

233 The main focus of this paper will be the *20.7k* simulation described in Romé
 234 et al (2022). The *20.7k* simulation differs from *CTRL_LGM* only by the addition of

235 a **constant** meltwater discharge corresponding to the **20.7 ka BP** slice of GLAC-
236 1D meltwater history derived by the protocol introduced in [Romé et al \(2022\)](#). For
237 each time step of the GLAC-1D ice sheet reconstruction, freshwater discharge was
238 computed from changes in ice sheet elevation at each grid cell and routed to an ocean
239 grid cell using an offline drainage map of the last glacial maximum ([Ivanovic et al,](#)
240 [2016](#)). Surface freshwater saturation (i.e. a grid cell salinity of 0 g kg^{-1}) can be reached
241 in some grid cells when large freshwater fluxes are recorded. To avoid this situation,
242 the meltwater is spread across a wider (proximal ocean) region around the source grid
243 box. Spreading regions are in the order of 10^6 km^2 , about a hundred ocean grid cells, an
244 area comparable to a typical Heinrich event ([Roberts et al, 2014](#)). From this meltwater
245 forcing history, we derive the freshwater pattern corresponding to the time slice we
246 are interested in, in this case 20.7 ka BP. This pattern will be called the meltwater
247 snapshot and used as a constant forcing for the 10,000 integration years. Independently
248 from the freshwater discharge, we change the global mean salinity target to match the
249 meltwater snapshot, in this case $35.8255 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ for 20.7 ka BP.

250 To get a more precise picture of the ocean dynamics in our simulations, we repeated
251 the *20.7k* simulation for 4,000 years, saving an extra set of salinity diagnostics, or salin-
252 ity tendencies, in the model output. This simulation is called *20.7k_tdc*. [Armstrong](#)
253 [et al \(2022\)](#) introduced the HadCM3 tendencies diagnosis and included a comprehen-
254 sive description of the implementation. We summarise the essential information in
255 Section [S6](#).

256 We included two additional simulations from [Romé et al \(2022\)](#) for comparison.
257 The *21k* simulation used the meltwater snapshot corresponding to 21 ka BP, a global
258 salinity target of $35.8334 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and was run for 4,000 years. The *18.2k* simulation
259 used the meltwater snapshot corresponding to 18.2 ka BP, a global salinity target of
260 $35.7348 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$ and was run for 10,000 years. Finally, we investigated the impact of the
261 global salinity target by running a simulation with the salinity correction algorithm

262 turned off. This simulation, called *20.7k_no_gst*, used the same meltwater snapshot as
263 *20.7k* and was run for 3,000 years.

3 Anatomy of the simulations

264 Romé et al (2022) introduced a method for clustering the meltwater snapshot sim-
265 ulations between different convection modes characterising the North Atlantic deep
266 water formation layouts. An *oscillating* simulation is characterised by the periodic
267 alternation of ‘warm’ modes – vigorous AMOC with relatively warm North Atlantic
268 temperatures – and ‘cold’ modes – weak AMOC with relatively cold North Atlantic
269 temperatures. The *20.7k* simulation is an example of an *oscillating* simulation where
270 this sequence can be observed in Figure 1a. If instead of sustained quasi-oscillations
271 the AMOC settles in a warm or cold steady state, the simulation is referred to as
272 a *warm* or *cold* simulation, respectively. The aim of Romé et al (2022) was not to
273 reproduce D-O cycles and we will therefore avoid using the commonly applied ‘sta-
274 dial’/‘interstadial’ terminology. Nonetheless, it can be helpful to think of warm and
275 cold modes in the light of interstadials and stadial states.

276 To characterise a simulation, we can look at its path in the state space projected
277 onto the Mixed Layer Depth (MLD) – an indicator of the mixing and convection of the
278 upper water column – in the GIN Seas against the MLD in the Irminger Sea (as plotted
279 in Figure 1b). A detail of the zones is given in Figure S1b. In this state space projection
280 (Figure 1b), we manually define five distinct *phases* of the oscillatory cycle. The *cold*
281 phase, where deep convection is weak in the North Atlantic; the *meridional warm*
282 phase (or simply *meridional* phase) with a main convection region in the GIN Seas
283 and an intermediate convection spot in the Irminger Sea; the *zonal warm* phase (or
284 simply *zonal* phase) dominated by convection in the Irminger Sea and low convection
285 in the GIN Seas; the *warming* phase, a transition from the *cold* phase to the *meridional*
286 phase and the *cooling* phase, a transition from the *zonal* phase to the *cold* phase. In

Fig. 1 Anatomy of the oscillations. (a) Time-series of AMOC index (maximum overturning circulation at 26.5° N) in the *20.7k* simulation. The background colour bars indicate the phases with *cold* in dark blue, *warming* in pink, the *meridional* in red, *zonal* in orange and *cooling* in light blue. Solid lines indicate the 30-year running mean and transparent lines the annual mean. (b) State space visualisation (i.e. scatter-plot) of the annual mean mixed layer depth in the Greenland Iceland Nordic (GIN) Seas against the mixed layer depth in the Irminger Sea (the zones are defined in Figure S1b). Each point corresponds to a year of the *20.7k* simulation time series after being processed by a low-pass filter with a cut-off frequency of $2 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{yr}^{-1}$ – the algorithm was described in Section S3. Shaded boxes define the phases shown in panel a. In the small globes, the composite mean winter (DJF) mixed layer depth is plotted for the *cold* and the two *warm* phases.

287 this paper’s simulations, the transition from the *meridional* to the *zonal* phase is too
 288 fast to be considered a distinct phase. Each phase was assigned a colour, and coloured
 289 bars will be shown in time series plots of this article in the style of Figure 1a.

290 The *oscillating 20.7k* simulation evolves along a well-defined cycle with a period-
291 icity of about 1,540 years (see Section S3). After an initial drop to a *cold* phase, it
292 starts by *warming* from the *cold* phase to the *meridional* phase, switching to the *zonal*
293 phase after a few hundred years before *cooling* back to the *cold* phase. The surface
294 temperature in Greenland typically varies by 8 °C over the course of an oscillation
295 (Romé et al, 2022). It takes a couple of cycles for the pattern to become more regular
296 as the climate system has completely adjusted to the freshwater perturbation and the
297 change of salinity target, and we will therefore refer to the first ~4000 years as the
298 *transient* regime.

299 The AMOC time series and state space plots of the *18.2k*, *21k*, *20.7k_no_gst* and
300 *20.7k_tdc* simulations are shown in Figure S2. Across all simulations, the modes are
301 associated with the same convective dynamics as the phases of the oscillators, although
302 they span slightly different areas on the two-dimensional MLD state space projection
303 due to the different freshwater release patterns. Note that in the general case, we call
304 a *warming* mode a transition between a *cold* mode to any *warm* mode and a *cooling*
305 mode from any *warm* mode to a *cold* mode. The *CTRL-LGM* simulation is a *warm*
306 simulation at a steady state in a *zonal* mode. All meltwater release simulations respond
307 to the initial meltwater release with a multi-centennial drop of the AMOC. The *21k*
308 simulation then recovers into a *zonal* steady state and thus is classified into the *warm*
309 simulations, similarly to the *20.7k_no_gst* simulation that follows one oscillatory cycle
310 before stabilising in a *zonal* steady state. On the other hand, the *18.2k* simulation
311 mostly remains in a *cold* steady state after the initial perturbation, albeit interrupted
312 by short-lived excitations into the *meridional* mode. Because of the irregular and
313 transient nature of these excitations, this simulation is categorised as a *cold* simulation.
314 Finally, even though the *oscillating 20.7k* and *20.7k_tdc* simulations are effectively
315 the same experiment, the noise introduced when the model was restarted to initialise
316 the salinity tendencies diagnostics (a process called 'reconfiguration') results in slight

317 differences in the periodicity and shape of the oscillations (Figure S2a,e,f,j). This is
318 due to the chaotic nature of the climate system, and we consider the two simulations
319 dynamically equivalent.

4 Results

4.1 Stratification changes at the North Atlantic deep water formation sites

320 The strength of the AMOC depends on the intensity of the convection at the North
321 Atlantic deep water formation sites, which in turn depends on the vertical stratification
322 of the water column. The stratification can be inferred from the density profile in
323 Figure 2p-r, plotted here for the 20.7k simulation between the *upper* waters (above
324 550 meters deep) the *intermediate* waters (550 to 1800 meters deep), and the *deep*
325 waters (below 1800 meters deep). The depth slices were chosen so that the *intermediate*
326 waters always lie outside of the mixed layer boundaries while still feeling the influence
327 of the upper waters' changes in temperature and salinity. In this section, we focused
328 our analysis on the GIN, Irminger and Iceland basins (Figure S1b). We only included
329 the last two cycles of the simulation to ensure minimum interference with the transient
330 regime at the start of the simulations. A comprehensive mapping of the North Atlantic
331 and Arctic ocean profiles is included in Figure S4. We consider the conclusions of the
332 following analysis to be the same between the Arctic basin and the Nordic Seas, and
333 the Labrador Sea and the Irminger Sea.

334 During the *cold* phase, **high stratification** prevents deep convection in the North
335 Atlantic. The deep water formation (diagnosed through mixed layer depth, Figure 2d-
336 f) and the North Atlantic subpolar gyre strength (Figure 2g,h) are at their weakest.
337 Winter sea ice extends down to the Iceland Basin, and the Nordic seas are covered
338 with ice all year long (Figure 2a-c). The low density of the upper North Atlantic

Fig. 2 North Atlantic dynamics at deep water formation sites. Plotted for the 20.7k simulation in the GIN Seas (*left*), the Irminger Sea (*middle*) and the Iceland Basin (*right*). The geographical zones are defined in Figure S1, and the background shading corresponds to the phases defined in Figure 1. (*a-c*) Early spring (March) and early autumn (September) sea ice concentration. (*d-f*) Annual mean mixed layer depth. (*g-i*) Annual mean anti-clockwise barotropic stream function indicating gyre circulation strength. (*j-l*) Annual mean temperature in the upper, intermediate and deep depth slices. (*m-o*) Annual mean salinity in the upper, intermediate and deep depth slices. (*p-r*) Annual mean density in the upper, intermediate and deep depth slices. In panels (*a-i*), solid lines indicate the 30-year running mean and transparent lines the annual mean.

339 (Figure 2*p-r*) is due to a deficit in salinity (Figure 2*m-n*), as well as higher temper-
340 atures in the GIN and Irminger seas (Figure 2*j,k*). This high stratification tends to
341 decrease throughout the *cold* phase, and in particular in the GIN Seas through the
342 combined effect of subsurface warming (warming under the mixed layer, most evi-
343 dent in intermediate waters temperatures) over the entire water column (Figure 2*j*),
344 a salinity increase of the upper waters and a salinity decrease of the intermediate and
345 deep waters (Figure 2*m*).

346 During the *warming* phase, the **stratification decreases** abruptly. The salin-
347 ification of the upper GIN Seas gains momentum while the intermediate and deep
348 waters keep freshening (Figure 2*m*). As deep convection recovers (Figure 2*d*) and sea
349 ice retreats (Figure 2*a*), the heat accumulated under the ice is evacuated to the atmo-
350 sphere (Figure 2*j*) further accelerating the stratification decrease (Figure 2*p*). Similar
351 effects are observed in the Irminger Sea (Figure 2*q*) and in the Iceland Basin (Figure
352 2*r*), although the changes in the density profile are less abrupt.

353 At the end of the warming phase, deep water formation resumes in the North
354 Atlantic (Figure 2*d-f*), marking the start of the *warm* phases characterised by **low**
355 **stratification**. At the onset of the *meridional* phase, the subpolar gyre is reactivated
356 (Figure 2*e*) and sea ice cover reaches a minimum in the GIN Seas and the Iceland Basin
357 (Figure 2*a,c*). The density gradient reduces between the upper and deep waters (Figure
358 2*p-r*), mostly driven by a drop in the upper waters salinity (Figure 2*m-o*), salinity
359 gradient, resulting in a minimum of stratification in the entire North Atlantic. In the
360 GIN Seas, this minimum only lasts for a few hundred years before upper salinity starts
361 to decrease again (Figure 2*m,p*). This decline eventually leads the deep convection
362 to shut down (Figure 2*d*), preceding a sharp recovery of the subpolar gyre strength
363 and of the Irminger Sea deep water formation, marking the start of the *zonal* phase.
364 During the *zonal* phase, the slow decrease of upper waters salinity is compensated for
365 by a reduction of the temperatures (Figure 2*j-o*), and the density profiles are mostly

366 unaltered (Figure 2*q-s*). Sea ice extent, however, is consistently increasing both in
367 summer (Figure 2*a*) and winter (Figure 4.1*b,c*). Disruptions appear at the end of the
368 *zonal* phase, when the salinity decrease in upper waters intensifies (Figure 2*o*) and is
369 no longer compensated for by subsurface heat evacuation (Figure 2*l*).

370 This triggers the start of the *cooling* phase where **stratification increases**
371 abruptly. The subpolar gyre shrinks (Figure 2*e*), subsurface heat accumulation restarts
372 (Figure 2*d-f*) and the salinity decreases further in the upper waters (Figure 2*m-o*). The
373 intermediate waters density reduction does not match the pace of the upper waters
374 (Figure 2*p-r*), leading to a collapse of deep convection in the North Atlantic (Figure
375 2*d-f*) and a return to a *cold* phase.

376 In this section, we showed that stratification changes are due to the combined effect
377 of salinity fluxes and subsurface heat accumulation at the deep water formation sites.
378 While the thermal effect can be linked to changes in sea ice cover, there is no obvious
379 explanation for the vertical salinity changes through dynamical processes within the
380 North Atlantic. A deeper analysis of the global salinity transfers is therefore required.

4.2 Global salt exchanges regulating North Atlantic salinity

381 Fluxes of salt in and out of the cluster formed by the North Atlantic and Arctic basins,
382 referred to as the *North Atlantic waters* in the rest of the analysis, can disrupt the
383 stratification of the deep water formation sites. Figure 3*a* shows that in the 20.7*k*
384 simulation, these two regions experience mean salinity shifts larger than in any other
385 basins (Figure S5, the zones used in this paragraph are defined in Figure S1*a*). Between
386 the *cold* and *warm* phases, the mean salinity changes by around 0.2 g kg^{-1} in the
387 North Atlantic and 0.35 g kg^{-1} in the Arctic, reaching up to 0.75 g kg^{-1} in the North
388 Atlantic and 1.1 g kg^{-1} in the Arctic if we restrict the domain to the first 550 meters
389 of the water column (Figure S5). Such variations of mean salinity only take small
390 changes in the salinity budgets (Figure 3*b*) because of the relatively small volume of

Fig. 3 Inter-basin salinity oscillations. Time-series of the *20.7k* simulation anomaly relative to the *CTRL_LGM* simulation for (a) mean salinity and (b) salt content. Background shading indicates the phases defined in Figure 1. Cross-correlation between the normalised salinity budget anomalies and AMOC index (see Figure 1a) in (c) the North Atlantic waters, (d) the Subtropical Atlantic waters and (e) the Deep waters domain. The lag phase in the cross-correlations is calculated with the 1540-year periodicity derived in Section S3. For readability purposes, only the signals from the upper and deep Arctic, North Atlantic, subtropical Atlantic, Southern Ocean and Pacific are plotted in the foreground in Figure 3c-e, with the other cross-correlations visible in the background.

391 these two basins. We observe a strong correlation between the AMOC time series and
 392 the salinity content in the North Atlantic waters in Figure 3c. This implies that the
 393 AMOC is the main driver behind salinity changes in the domain. The North Atlantic
 394 waters' salinity reaches its minimum roughly at the same time as the AMOC index
 395 (~ 750 years after its maximum, Figure 3c), but the North Atlantic waters' salinity
 396 variations are more muted than the AMOC signal during the cold mode.

397 The subtropical Atlantic mean salinity is ahead of the North Atlantic signal by
 398 ~ 500 years (Figure 3a,d). The correlation and anti-correlation coefficients are around

399 0.8 and -0.8 , respectively, due to less sharp phase transitions in the subtropical
400 Atlantic salinity signal. Despite large changes in the salt budget (Figure 3b), the mean
401 salinity in the subtropical Atlantic varies by less than 0.1 g kg^{-1} throughout the simu-
402 lation (Figure 3a). The subtropical Atlantic signal is echoed in the deep North Atlantic
403 and the upper South Atlantic, forming another domain that we call the *Subtropical*
404 *waters*. The upper layer of the Pacific basin follows a similar trend but is delayed by
405 ~ 200 years compared to the *Subtropical waters*. To conserve global salt content (see
406 Section 2.2), the large changes of salt content in the *Subtropical waters* have to be
407 compensated for in other basins.

408 We find changes proportional but of opposite sign to the salinity in the *Subtropical*
409 *waters* in the Pacific and, to a lower extent, the Southern oceans (Figure 3b). The salt
410 content anomaly in these basins is dominated by the intermediate and deep water sig-
411 nal (below 550 meters, Figure S6). This domain, which we call the *Deep waters*, shows
412 less spatial coherence as changes in the deep waters (below 1800 meters) experience a
413 delay of ~ 250 years compared to changes in the intermediate waters (e.g. Pacific sig-
414 nal in Figure 4.2e). Overall, the *deep waters* signal lags behind the AMOC signal by
415 ~ 250 years, and its opposite signal leads the AMOC by ~ 500 years.

416 In summary, the global salt fluxes resemble a relaxation oscillator where salt is
417 slowly transported from the deep Pacific reservoir to the upper waters of the Atlantic
418 during the *cold* phases, and exported from the Atlantic to the Pacific during the
419 *warm* phases (Figure 3b). Salt anomalies in the North Atlantic are remarkably coupled
420 to changes in the AMOC strength and follow the *Subtropical* and *Deep* waters salt
421 exchanges with a 500-year delay. The global salt redistribution influences the North
422 Atlantic stratification changes described in Section 4.1, and both components come
423 together to explain the mechanisms for the AMOC oscillations that will be described
424 in Section 5.

5 The convection-advection oscillator mechanism

425 In this section, we introduce the **convection-advection oscillator** mechanism to
426 explain the millennial-scale variability simulated in *20.7k*. This mechanism, sum-
427 marised in Figure 4, is based on the fast/slow components coupling framework
428 introduced in (Roberts and Saha, 2017). The North Atlantic deep water formation
429 activation in response to stratification thresholds makes up the **fast convection**
430 component, and the large scale reorganisation of global salt content changing buoy-
431 ancy fluxes in the North Atlantic makes up the **slow advection** component. During
432 *cold* phases, the North Atlantic stratification is high and the AMOC is weak (Figure
433 2). Salt accumulation in the subtropical Atlantic (Figure 3*b*) leaks into the North
434 Atlantic (Figure 2*p*) while the accumulation of subsurface heat decreases the deep
435 water formation sites' stratification (Figure 2*p*). In about 500 years, the gradual drop
436 of stratification passes a threshold where the fast convection component is reactivated.
437 There is a positive feedback loop between the strengthening of North Atlantic deep
438 convection and salt advection into the Upper North Atlantic that leads to the abrupt
439 acceleration of the AMOC. After a transition to a *warm* phase, the North Atlantic
440 stratification is low and the AMOC is strong (Figure 2*o,r*). The overturning circula-
441 tion flushes the salt excess to the deep oceans, and the Atlantic becomes progressively
442 salt depleted (Figure 3*b*), reducing its upper water density. This slow decrease lasts
443 for 500 to 1000 years and the southwards transport of sea ice in the North Atlantic
444 (Figure 2*a-c*) progressively resumes the subsurface warming (Figure 2*k,l*). A more
445 abrupt drop is observed at the start of the *cooling* period when a new threshold is
446 crossed and the fast convection component is reactivated. The positive feedback loop
447 between the decrease of North Atlantic convection and the slowdown of salt import
448 into the North Atlantic leads to the deactivation of the AMOC and the system returns
449 to a *cold* phase.

Fig. 4 The oscillator mechanism. Millennial-scale variability mechanism observed in 20.7k. The colours correspond to the phases defined in Figure 1 to the regions defined in Figure S1.

450 The **meltwater discharge** creates a fresh surface layer in the North Atlantic that
451 reduces the upper salinity and can lead to deep water formation deactivation when
452 targeted at deep convection sites (see Section 4 by Romé et al (2022)). The decrease
453 of upper water salinity triggers an initial shift from the *control zonal* phase to a *cold*
454 phase before the deep waters have time to adapt to the perturbation. This transition
455 happens in the first few hundred years and kickstart the oscillator. It takes two to
456 three cycles until the end of the transient regime where the influence of the freshwater
457 perturbation is observed, for instance, in the deep density profiles in Figure S4). For
458 this reason, we focus the following analysis on the last three cycles of the *oscillating*
459 simulation. In the rest of the run, the constant meltwater input acts to decrease the
460 upper North Atlantic density.

461 The rest of this analysis relies on the more detailed information gathered from
462 the salinity tendency diagnostics presented in Section S6. In order to reactivate North
463 Atlantic convection, the freshwater forcing needs to be compensated for by salinity
464 fluxes into the North Atlantic basin: this is the role of the **slow advection** component.
465 The subtropical Atlantic is a net evaporation basin and tends to accumulate salt in
466 the absence of the AMOC advective flux (Figure 3b, Figure S9). This excess of salt is
467 eventually transferred to the upper North Atlantic by gyre circulation and diffusion
468 (Figure S8), increasing the upper North Atlantic density (Figure 2p-rFigure S12).
469 When the AMOC is reactivated, the salt excess is progressively evacuated from the
470 upper North Atlantic to the deep ocean through convection (Figure 3e, Figure S4),
471 and then redistributed along the oceanic pathway. The global salinity transfer can be
472 seen as a salinity anomaly slowly moving between the subtropical Atlantic and the
473 Pacific (Weijer and Dijkstra, 2003), and it takes more than a thousand years for the
474 waters for the global salinity exchanges to reach a new equilibrium state (Figure 3b).

475 The combination of salt fluxes entering the North Atlantic, subsurface warming and
476 sea ice transport modify stratification at the deep water formation sites and trigger

477 the **fast convection component**. During the *cold* phases, the insulating effect of
478 sea ice described by Marcott et al (2011) led to a warming and density drop of the
479 entire water column (Figure S12). This effect is the most prominent at high latitudes,
480 including the GIN Seas, where the sea ice is perennial (Figure 2*a,p*). In the upper
481 North Atlantic waters, the sea ice effect is superseded by the salinity input from
482 the subtropical Atlantic (Figure S12*a-c*). In the GIN Seas, a vertical stratification is
483 eventually crossed leading to the reactivation of deep convection in this region. The salt
484 advection feedback (Drijfhout et al, 2015; Weijer et al, 2019) accelerate this transition
485 into a *warming* phase.

486 During the *warm* phases, the decreasing salt availability in the subtropical Atlantic
487 reduces upper North Atlantic water density (Figure S8), and the slow evacuation of
488 subsurface heat accumulated in the Irminger and Iceland basins during the cold phase
489 increases deep waters density (Figure S13). Despite the gradually expanding sea ice
490 in the North Atlantic, the absence of a clear salinity signal in the region that would
491 indicate the brine rejection (Figure S8) indicate that the sea ice is more likely to be
492 transported in rather than formed in the regions. Instead, further reduction of upper
493 water density (Figure 2*p-r*) can be linked to an increase of temperatures resulting
494 from the insulating effect of sea ice (Figure S13*d-h*). As the stratification increases, it
495 crosses a threshold where the positive feedback leads to a sharp decline of the AMOC.

6 Sensitivity of the convection-advection mechanism to climate conditions

496 To gain insight into the range of climate conditions under which the convection-
497 advection oscillator mechanism (Section 5) is active, we extend our analysis to the
498 additional glacial meltwater experiments. A comparison of the dynamics of the main
499 simulations in this article is given in Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Comparison to the non-oscillating simulations. 30-year running means (solid lines) and annual mean (transparent lines) time series for (*a-c*) maximum AMOC strength, (*d-f*) winter sea ice concentration, (*g-i*) salinity budgets in global ocean basins (see Figure 3*a*), (*j-l*) N2 stratification index (Li et al. 2020) in the deep water formation sites (low negative values indicate high stratification) and (*m-o*) ocean potential temperature profiles in the North Atlantic for three meltwater snapshot simulations (see Table 1). The abrupt increase of Pacific salinity in panels *j* and *k* correspond to a change of the basin volume introduced by the bathymetry smoothing algorithm in the Philippines described by Romé et al (2022).

500 The magnitude of the freshwater perturbation is critical for sustaining the oscil-
501 lations. In the *21k* simulation, a weaker freshwater forcing compared to the *20.7k*
502 simulation does not significantly alter the global salt distribution (Figure 5*i*). The
503 AMOC index only drops by 5 Sv (Figure 5*c*) and the salinity anomaly is dispersed
504 before a stratification threshold is crossed in the North Atlantic (Figure 5*l*). The *21k*
505 simulation eventually recovers to a *zonal* steady state, the sea ice edge settles after
506 another 500 years (Figure 5*f*), and the simulation shows no further signs of instability.
507 The *warm steady state* simulations, such as the *21k* simulation, behave like an over-
508 damped oscillator: the applied forcing transiently kicks the system out of the initial
509 state, but the system returns to a warm state after less than a thousand years. This
510 suggests that the zonal state retains its stability and that the simulation remains in
511 its basin of attraction following the onset of the forcing.

512 In the *18.2k* simulation, a strong meltwater input triggers a near-collapse of the
513 AMOC and high North Atlantic stratification (Figure 5*k*) prevents the recovery of
514 deep water formation. It takes about 1000 years for the global salinity distribution
515 to reach a new equilibrium (Figure 5*h*), without any stratification threshold being
516 crossed that could reinvigorate the AMOC. In the case of the *18.2k* simulation, there
517 are short-lived excursions from a stable *cold* state to a transient *meridional* state,
518 reminiscent of *excitable* behaviour. The *cold* simulations are therefore defined as *cold*
519 *excitable steady state* simulation with the *cold* mode acting as an attractor. As an
520 alternative to multistable, oscillatory or resonant dynamics, Riechers et al (2024)
521 conducted a study where an excitable monostable model can capture the shape of D-O
522 cycles. In our case, the *18.2k* simulation does not resemble D-O variability because of
523 short warm modes and the absence of slow cooling. The AMOC recoveries result from
524 the warming of the North Atlantic water column visible in Figure 5*n*, fuelled by sea
525 ice accumulation over the deep water formation sites (Figure 5*e*). The recoveries are
526 strictly confined to the GIN Seas, and the stratification of the Irminger Sea remains too

527 high to transition into a *zonal* steady state. In other words, the salinity import from the
528 subtropical Atlantic is not strong enough to compensate for the freshwater forcing and,
529 therefore, to trigger the positive feedback that would reactivate the AMOC. Although
530 the excursions into a *meridional* mode occur at what seems to be random intervals,
531 their frequency increases over time due to continuous subsurface heat accumulation,
532 indicating that the asymptotic state may not have been reached.

533 In between the *warm steady state* and the *cold excitable steady state*, the *oscillating*
534 simulations are obtained in a small window of opportunity where the freshwater forcing
535 is strong enough to trigger a *cold* mode, but not too strong to prevent a subsequent
536 transition to one of the *warm* modes. In this window of opportunity, the solution is
537 attracted to a chaotic limit cycle (closed curve in the state space) around which it
538 evolves quasi-periodically. Possibly, the warm mode undergoes a supercritical Hopf
539 bifurcation as the freshwater input is increased at the relevant locations, giving rise to
540 stable oscillations (Boers et al, 2022). Finally, small changes in meltwater discharge can
541 modify the shape and periodicity of the oscillations described by Romé et al (2022),
542 but do not change the underlying mechanism.

7 The scope of application of the convection-advection oscillator mechanism

543 The *convection-advection* oscillator mechanism presented here was identified in the
544 *20.7k* simulation introduced in Romé et al (2022), and its relevance may depend on
545 the simulation inputs, the model settings and the choice of the model. The comparison
546 to Armstrong et al (2022)'s simulations, using the same version of the model, indicates
547 that several mechanisms for millennial-scale variability can coexist within one model.
548 Armstrong et al (2022) use the 30 ka BP background climate in which the Irminger
549 Sea and European coast convection sites are still active during the cold modes, and
550 they can trigger spontaneous oscillations in the absence of additional freshwater. The

551 *convection-advection* oscillator should be seen as a new occurrence of a *fast-slow* oscil-
552 lator (see Figure S15) based on the concept of a relaxation oscillator (Pikovsky et al,
553 2001; Crucifix, 2012; Roberts and Saha, 2017). Although its specific interplay of fast
554 and slow processes is new, the building blocks of the mechanism have been identified in
555 former studies. For example, Klockmann et al (2020) and Vettoretti and Peltier (2018)
556 highlighted the role of the subtropical Atlantic salt accumulation and depletion. The
557 difference of time response between the upper and lower waters in the North Atlantic
558 as a driver of instability is central to the deep-decoupling oscillations theory (Win-
559 ton and Sarachik, 1993), and observed in Vettoretti and Peltier (2018) and Kuniyoshi
560 et al (2022). The hypothesis that salt oscillations can reach further than the Atlantic
561 basin was introduced in Weijer and Dijkstra (2003). The insulating effect of sea ice
562 is similar to the one described by Kuniyoshi et al (2022). Finally, the response of the
563 North Atlantic convection to changes in stratification fits well with the description in
564 Vettoretti and Peltier (2018).

565 On the other hand, our *convection-advection* oscillator does not include previously
566 proposed *slow* components such as changes of Southern Ocean density (e.g., Oka et al,
567 2021; Vettoretti et al, 2022). These changes can modify the Atlantic stratification in
568 models with a strong sensitivity of the AABW to the Southern Ocean dynamics, but
569 in the *20.7k* simulation the small density increase and decrease due to the shrinking
570 and expansion of the AABW during the cold and warm phases, respectively, are too
571 weak to significantly impact the North Atlantic convection (Figure S14). Arctic sea
572 ice transport (e.g., Vettoretti and Peltier, 2018) is at play in our simulations, but sea
573 ice formation and melting appear to play a lesser role than inter-basin salt transport
574 in regards to the North Atlantic salinity changes, contrary to Vettoretti and Peltier
575 (2018) or Armstrong et al (2022). Armstrong et al (2022) also identify large changes
576 of precipitation and evaporation in the Atlantic as a driver of the salt oscillator. This

577 tendency is not dominant in our simulations (Fig. S8). The *fast* components control-
578 ling the reactivation of deep water formation sites can also be the result of different
579 physical processes in different experiments. Klockmann et al (2020) and Armstrong
580 et al (2022) discuss the role of wind driven-feedback in the abrupt re(de)activation of
581 deep water formation. There is no clear evidence of a similar phenomenon happening
582 in our simulations. Additionally, both Vettoretti and Peltier (2016) and Kuniyoshi et al
583 (2022), associate the overshoot phase with polynyas opening in the sea-ice-covered
584 Irminger Sea, a phenomenon that is not observed in any of our simulations. Finally,
585 the regularity of the oscillations indicates a weak role of stochastic forcing in *20.7k*
586 (Figure S3), but may play a major role in *18.2k*.

587 Another peculiarity of our oscillating simulations is the existence of two warm
588 states and the transition from a *meridional* to a *zonal* phase. Cheng et al (2011) sim-
589 ulated a similar two-step warming phase, but in their case the abrupt recovery of deep
590 water formation was observed first in the Labrador Sea and then in the GIN Seas.
591 In this simulation, the transition is smooth and the *meridional* phase is akin to an
592 **overshoot phase** of the *zonal* phase, a phenomenon regularly simulated in GCM
593 millennial-scale variability (Peltier and Vettoretti, 2014; Kuniyoshi et al, 2022; Vet-
594 toretti et al, 2022, e.g.). It happens when deep water formation shifts from the GIN
595 Seas to the Irminger Sea due to local reorganisation of convection and gyre circulation
596 (Figure S8). The *meridional* phase witnesses a drop in the advective flux of salt into the
597 North Atlantic (Figure S8b,d) that leads to a negative salinity import into the basin
598 (Figure S8c), making this phase unstable. While the transition from a *meridional* to
599 a *zonal* phase is not an essential part of the overarching convection-advection mecha-
600 nism, it may play a more central role in other simulations using different experiment
601 configurations. It is possible that, for instance, longer *meridional* phases can be sus-
602 tained in simulations where the salinity tendency inversion in the North Atlantic is
603 not obtained, such as in the *17.8k* simulation in Romé et al (2022).

604 The combination of fast and slow components involved in millennial-scale variabil-
605 ity implies a multiplicity of possible mechanisms, probably leading to different shapes,
606 duration and regularity of the oscillations. In *20.7k*, the pace of the simulations is set
607 by two limiting processes. During the *cold* phase, it takes about 500 years for a suf-
608 ficient amount of salt to leak from the subtropical Atlantic into the North Atlantic
609 in order to cross a North Atlantic stratification threshold. In the *warm* phases, the
610 salt anomaly takes more than a thousand years to travel across the entire track of
611 the overturning circulation to reach the Subtropical Atlantic. These two processes are
612 dependent on model parametrisation and input fields. Other factors impacting the
613 emergence of sustained oscillations could be associated with slow components such
614 as the rate of Arctic sea ice transport (Vettoretti and Peltier, 2018) or the bipolar
615 see-saw (Crowley, 1992; Stocker, 1998).

616 In Section 5, we showed that the convection-advection mechanism requires the
617 propagation of a salinity anomaly between the ocean basins. One of the main param-
618 eters that can impact global salt distribution is the choice of the salinity conservation
619 scheme. In our simulations, the ice sheet extent does not vary with the meltwater dis-
620 charge, and therefore requires the use of a global salinity conservation algorithm to
621 prevent salinity drifts (see Section 2.2 Dentith et al, 2019). In order to test the effect
622 of the salinity conservation scheme on the convection-advection mechanism, we ran a
623 simulation without any salinity conservation: the *20.7k_no_gst* simulation. This sim-
624 ulation follows the evolution of the *20.7k* simulation for the first 500 years (Figure
625 S16a,b) before the salt distribution becomes unstable at the end of the *cold* phase: the
626 salinity of all the oceans then increases in every basin during the *zonal* phase (Figure
627 S16c,d). In this configuration, the tropical Atlantic salt content is in excess, and the
628 North Atlantic upper density remains high, maintaining active deep-water formation
629 (Figure S16f), pushing the system away from the window of opportunity. Salt accu-
630 mulation may seem counter-intuitive in a freshwater hosing experiment, but the rigid

631 lid parametrisation prevents the model from fully resolving the water cycle (Demory
632 et al, 2014), which can lead to these unrealistic drifts. In addition to its role in closing
633 the water budget, the applied salinity correction is a way to emulate the stabilising
634 power of dynamical ice sheets on global salinity. This phenomenon could play an active
635 role in the occurrence of millennial-scale variability: Wickert et al (2023), for instance,
636 proposed a mechanism where the storage and release of freshwater in the Laurentide
637 ice sheet during the stadials and interstadials, respectively, can provide a negative
638 feedback that impedes the deglaciation of the ice sheet. On the other hand, there are
639 certain times during the last glacial period when the meltwater released by the desta-
640 bilisation of the ice sheets, such as during Heinrich events (Menviel et al, 2014, 2020)
641 or saddle collapse (Gregoire et al, 2012; Ivanovic et al, 2017), has acted as a driver
642 for abrupt environmental change. This makes the case for further coupled-climate ice
643 sheet experiments (e.g., Alvarez-Solas et al, 2019; Schannwell et al, 2024; Mikolajew-
644 icz et al, 2024) in order to include prognostic feedbacks from the ice sheets and better
645 constrain the freshwater forcing during the last glacial period and deglaciation.

8 Conclusion

646 We presented a mechanism explaining the millennial-scale variability observed in a
647 last glacial maximum HadCM3 general circulation model simulation, forced with a
648 constant pattern of deglacial meltwater. The simulation displays a periodic evolution
649 along a limit cycle through a *cold* phase – where the AMOC is weak and there is no
650 deep water formation in the North Atlantic, a *meridional warm* phase – where the
651 AMOC is strong and convection predominates in the Nordic seas, and a *zonal warm*
652 phase – where the AMOC is strong and convection shifts primarily to the Irminger
653 Sea.

654 The convection-advection oscillator is composed of a *slow advection* component and
655 a *fast convection* component, with the AMOC coupling the two. The *slow advection*

656 component transports a salt anomaly between the subtropical Atlantic and mainly the
657 deep Pacific. The *fast convection* component responds to thresholds in North Atlantic
658 stratification by reactivating or deactivating deep water formation sites, amplified by
659 the positive salt-advection feedback. During *cold* phases, the salt accumulates in the
660 subtropical Atlantic and slowly leaks into the North Atlantic to increase its upper-
661 ocean density. In addition, progressive subsurface warming decreases the deep density
662 in sea ice-covered regions. This leads to a decrease in the stratification of the Nordic
663 Seas until reaching a threshold where convection rapidly reactivates. The resulting
664 *meridional* phase acts as an overshoot mode before deep water formation shifts to a
665 predominantly *zonal* configuration. During the *warm* phases, the Atlantic becomes
666 depleted in salt because of the slow circulation of the subtropical salt anomaly along
667 the deep ocean pathway. In the North Atlantic, the subsurface heat accumulated
668 during *cold* phases is progressively being evacuated, while the upper waters remain
669 warm due to southwards sea ice transport into the North Atlantic. The salt and
670 temperature changes lead to a slow increase in the stratification of the Irminger Sea
671 and Iceland Basin. The *cold* mode ends when deep convection reaches a threshold of
672 deactivation, leading to a rapid weakening of the AMOC driven by the salt-advection
673 feedback.

674 Starting from the AMOC control state, the model is forced with the respective
675 deglacial freshwater pattern at the beginning of each simulation. This perturbation
676 has to be strong enough to deactivate the North Atlantic deep water formation sites,
677 but not too strong to allow for the crossing of a threshold from a *cold* mode back
678 into a *warm* mode within the span of the global salt redistribution. In the absence of
679 salinity correction, the global salinity anomaly between the Pacific and Subtropical
680 Atlantic is superseded by a global salinity drift, leading to an abnormally high upper
681 North Atlantic density and moving the system out of the window of opportunity.

682 The simulations analysed in the paper demonstrate the concept of a window
683 of opportunity, associated with meltwater discharge. Depending on the forcing, we
684 observe a *warm steady state* simulation where the system sustains North Atlantic
685 deep water formation despite the freshwater input, a *limit cycle* simulation where the
686 system follows the convection-advection oscillator mechanism, and an *excitable cold*
687 *steady state* simulation, where a persistence in the weak AMOC state is interrupted
688 by short-lived recoveries of North Atlantic convection. Further sensitivity experiments
689 involving a more comprehensive range of boundary conditions (such as atmospheric
690 greenhouse gas concentrations, orbital parameters, ice sheet geometry, salinity con-
691 servation scheme), climate forcing and physical parameter settings are needed to
692 categorically constrain the regions in parameter space where these different behaviours
693 occur.

694 While model and boundary condition dependencies influence the results in any
695 study of simulated abrupt climate change, we are at an exciting juncture where com-
696 mon patterns between the different mechanisms presented across the literature are
697 starting to crystallise. This study evidences how concepts of dynamical systems the-
698 ory can guide the analysis of model simulations towards a unified understanding of
699 millennial-scale climate variability. Finally, in the absence of dynamical ice sheets,
700 salinity conservation is a necessary condition for obtaining millennial-scale oscillations
701 in our simulations, and the introduction of climate-ice sheet feedback would represent
702 a significant step towards simulations of more realistic millennial-scale variability.

703 **Supplementary information.** The article has accompanying supplementary infor-
704 mation that consists of Sections [S1](#) to [S8](#) and Figures [S1](#) to [S16](#).

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Declarations

- The authors declare no conflict of interest or competing interests.
- A prior version of this manuscript was published in YMR’s PhD thesis and can be accessed at <https://etheses.whiterose.ac.uk/34761/>.
- The data used to produce the Figures of this article are available on the CEDA archive under [Romé et al \(2024\)](#). Additional data can be requested to the corresponding author.
- The code used to produce the Figures of this article is available on Zenodo under [Romé \(2024\)](#).
- The authors are listed as per their estimated contribution to this article. YMR wrote the manuscript, ran the simulations, conducted the analysis and produced the figures. RI helped running the simulations, supervised the analysis and proofread the article. LJG supervised the analysis and proofread the article. DS provided the oceanic expertise in the definition of the mechanism and proofread the article. SST helped with the description of the mechanism and proofread the manuscript. RB helped with the theoretical framing of the analysis and proofread the manuscript.

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